

Transition Metal Complexes of 5-[4'-(Nitrophenyl)azo]salicylaldehyde-3-thiosemicarbazone

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Metal complexes formed by the interaction of 5-[4'-(nitrophenyl)azo]salicylaldehyde-3-thiosemicarbazone [HAT] with some bivalent metal ion have been prepared. The ligand behaves as neutral bidentate, as mononegative bidentate or tridentate ligand.

Thiosemicarbazide and thiosemicarbazone possess various important biological activities¹. Transition metal complexes of these ligands have been screened for medicinal properties². Also, thiosemicarbazone have many applications especially as reagents for the microdetermination of certain transition elements³. Here, we report the preparation of some transition metal complexes of Schiff base (1) derived from condensation of 5-[4'-(nitrophenyl)azo]salicylaldehyde with thiosemicarbazone.

Results and Discussion

Analytical and ir spectral data of the ligand and its metal complexes are listed in Table 1.

Ir spectrum (KBr) of the ligand HAT showed bands at 3340, 2983, 1599, 1340 and 950 cm^{-1} assignable to ν_{OH} , ν_{NH} , $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{N=N}}$, respectively. The bands at 3456 and 3167 cm^{-1} are assigned to the $\nu_{\text{as}}\text{NH}_2$ modes and the one at 3128 cm^{-1} to $\nu_{\text{s}}\text{NH}_2$ which did not undergo any perceptible shifts suggesting that there is no interaction between NH_2 group and the metal ion. The medium bands at 1289 and 780 cm^{-1} are due to $\nu_{\text{C=S}}$. The spectra did not display the $\nu_{\text{S-H}}$ mode at $\sim 2600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating that in the solid state the ligand remains in the thioketo form.

The ^1H nmr spectra (DMSO-d_6) of HAT showing the downfield shift of OH proton, can be related to the presence of an intramolecular equilibrium which suggests that thiol form predominates in solution and also indicates the presence of intramolecular hydrogen bonding. In the ^{13}C nmr spectrum of the ligand, two signals are observed at 177.9 (C=S) and 160.52 ppm (C=N).

HAT behaves as mononegative tridentate ligand via the azomethine nitrogen, the thion sulphur and the oxygen of hydroxyl group with displacement of hydrogen atom from the latter. This behavior is found in $\text{Ni}[\text{AT}]\text{Cl}$, $\text{Co}[\text{AT}]_2$, $\text{Hg}[\text{AT}]\text{Cl}$, $\text{Ni}[\text{AT}]\text{Ac}$, $\text{Cu}[\text{AT}]\text{Ac}$ and $\text{Cd}[\text{AT}]\text{Ac}$. This mode of complexation is supported by the lowering shift of

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND IR SPECTRAL (cm^{-1}) DATA FOR HAT AND ITS METAL COMPLEXES*

Compd.	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$	$\nu_{\text{C=S}}$	Metal %: Found/ (Calcd.)
$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{S}$ (Brown)	1599	1289	—
$\text{Ni}[\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{S}]\text{Cl}$ (Red)	1588	1263	13.68 (13.29)
$\text{Ni}[\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{S}]\text{CH}_3\text{COO}$ (Red)	1580	1263	12.84 (12.59)
$\text{Cu}[\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4\text{S}]\text{Cl}$ (Green)	1559	1290	13.21 (13.71)
$\text{Cu}[\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{S}]\text{CH}_3\text{COO}$ (Brown)	1588	1280	14.00 (13.53)
$\text{Co}[\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_{12}\text{O}_6\text{S}_2]$ (Violet)	1588	1277	8.12 (7.51)
$\text{Co}[\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_6\text{O}_5\text{S}]\text{CH}_3\text{COO}$ (Purple)	1586	1269	12.08 (11.86)
$\text{Cd}[\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{S}]\text{Cl}_2$ (Peige)	1567	1280	22.11 (21.58)
$\text{Cd}[\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_6\text{O}_5\text{S}]\text{CH}_3\text{COO}$ (Brown)	1586	1263	22.54 (22.08)
$\text{Pd}[\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4\text{S}]\text{Cl}$ (Brown)	1557	1289	22.00 (21.10)
$\text{Hg}[\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{S}]\text{Cl}$ (Black)	1563	1276	35.01 (34.82)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and Cl (where applicable) analyses.

C=N frequency (in some cases split into two band or doublet) due to partial overlapping of C=N, C=C and NH_2 vibrations⁷, and that of N=N to higher frequency indicating coordination through the azomethine group⁸. The disappearance of OH frequency indicates that the hydrogen proton is lost upon complexation and the involvement of this oxygen in bonding to the metal ion. Also the shift in the characteristic bands of C=S to lower frequency is a result of coordination through sulfur atom.

In addition, HAT may act as mononegative bidentate ligand coordinating via azomethine nitrogen and the deprotonated OH group. This is found in $\text{Co}[\text{AT}]\text{Ac} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cu}[\text{AT}]\text{Cl} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Pd}[\text{AT}]\text{Cl} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and confirmed by ir, through the disappearance OH band and shifting of C=N to lower wavenumber, indicating coordination by the azomethine nitrogen and oxygen of hydroxyl group. The

two characteristic bands for C=S group remained unchanged showing the non-involvement of the thion sulfur in bonding.

On the other hand, HAT may act as a neutral bidentate ligand coordinating via the thion sulfur and azomethine nitrogen. This behavior is found in Cd[HAT]Cl₂. The ir spectrum showed a strong band at 3343 cm⁻¹ (OH) similar to free ligand, indicating that this does not participate in the complexation, and the shift of C=N and C=S band to lower wavenumber. This confirmed the neutral bidentate nature of the ligand. The observed new bands in the complex at 575–510, 481–436, 415–380 and 338–281 cm⁻¹ are tentatively assigned to M–O⁹, M–N¹⁰, M–S¹¹ and M–Cl¹², respectively.

In Co[AT]₂ and Co[AT]Ac.2H₂O, the magnetic moment values are 5.12 and 5.01 B.M. respectively, which lie within the range reported for high-spin octahedral cobalt(II) complexes¹³. The electronic spectra (DMF) of these complexes showed bands at 18382–19456 and 25252–26911 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to ⁴1_g → ⁴T_{2g}(F) ν₂ and ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g}(P) ν₃ transitions¹⁴. The calculated Dq, B, β, ν₁ and ν₂/ν₁ values for Co[AT]₂ are 985 cm⁻¹, 1204 cm⁻¹, 1.23, 8524 cm⁻¹ and 2.15 and for Co[AT]Ac.2H₂O are 1043 cm⁻¹, 1286 cm⁻¹, 1.32, 9016 cm⁻¹ and 2.15 respectively. The values of ν₂/ν₁ indicate octahedral geometry.

The nickel complexes were found to be diamagnetic which suggests a square-planar 4-coordinates structure. The electronic spectra of these complexes exhibit two bands at 16666–20491 and 25152–26178 cm⁻¹, assignable to ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g} transitions in a square-planar geometry¹⁵. The fact that no band is observed below 10000 cm⁻¹ indicates square-planar stereochemistry for these complexes¹⁵, which may also be deduced from their red-brown color.

The room temperature magnetic moment of Cu[AT]Cl. H₂O and Cu[AT]Ac are 1.78 and 1.19 B.M. respectively. The observed value for Cu[AT]Cl.H₂O is in the range for high-spin copper(II) complex having monomeric structure¹⁶. The lower value of Cu[AT]Ac may be attributed to the covalent nature of the metal-sulfur bond or the polymeric structure. The electronic spectra of these complexes showed bands at 21834–22222 and 25380–27932 cm⁻¹ which may assigned to ²T_{2g} → ²E_g transition and charge transfer respectively¹⁷. The band position and magnetic moment are in a good agreement with those generally observed for square-planar copper(II) complexes^{18,19}.

The electronic spectrum of the diamagnetic palladium(II) complex showed broad band at 21367–22321 cm⁻¹ which is probably due to ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_{1g} transition in the square-planar geometry²⁰.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade.

Preparation of HAT : 5-[4'-(Nitrophenyl)azo]salicylaldehyde was prepared by coupling of diazotised *p*-nitroaniline with salicylaldehyde in basic medium. The ligand was prepared by refluxing 5-[4'-(nitrophenyl)azo]salicylaldehyde (25.5 g, 0.1 mol) and thiosemicarbazone (9.1 g, 0.1 mol) in MeOH (400 ml) for 2 h. The resulting brown precipitate was washed with EtOH and Et₂O and crystallized from EtOH, (m.p. 262°).

Preparation of complexes : A mixture of equimolar quantities (1 mmol) of the hydrated metal salts in EtOH and HAT was refluxed in EtOH. The volume of the solution was then reduced by evaporation and the resulting solids (60–75%) were washed with hot EtOH and Et₂O, dried and stored in a desiccator over CaCl₂. All measurements were carried out as described before²¹. The metal halide was determined by standard method²². Molecular weight was measured by Rast's method using camphor as solvent. All these complexes had m.p. above 200°.

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